

Annex to: Update of the risk assessment of mineral oil hydrocarbons in food.
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Annex H – Protocol for an Expert Knowledge Elicitation on the uncertainty of the risk assessment of mineral oil hydrocarbons in food

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H.1. Problem definition

The Expert Knowledge Elicitation is used to perform a quantitative uncertainty assessment for the main conclusion of the opinion.

H.1.1. Background description

Mineral oil hydrocarbons (MOH) considered in the mandate are hydrocarbons containing 10 to about 50 carbon atoms which have been divided into two main types: mineral oil saturated hydrocarbons (MOSH) and mineral oil aromatic hydrocarbons (MOAH). MOH are chemical compounds derived from crude oil. Some hydrocarbons synthetically produced from coal, natural gas and biomass are subsumed under MOH in analytical determinations. MOH can be present in food in many ways, such as environmental contamination, lubricants for machinery used during harvesting and food production, processing aids

like release agents or dust binders, food or feed additives and food contact materials. So-called “food grade” MOH products are treated in a way that the MOAH content is minimised.

Terms of Reference

- To assess the toxicity studies on mineral oil hydrocarbons which have become available since the EFSA scientific opinion on mineral oil hydrocarbons in 2012 and to update the scientific opinion if necessary as regards hazard characterisation.
- To provide an updated exposure assessment taking into account recent occurrence data.
- To update the section on risk characterisation, as necessary.

Subject	Description
Context	Mineral oils in food
Problem	Uncertainty analysis
Path to a solution RA model	Identification of main uncertainties Quantification of the effect on the main conclusion
Parameters for EKE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EKE on Effect Assessment parameter • EKE on Exposure Assessment parameter • Final Assessment
Mandate/Question	EFSA-Q-2020-00664
Panel	CONTAM
Working group	MOHs in Food
Responsible EFSA unit/team	CONTAM
Intended output	Final uncertainty assessment

H.1.2. Risk assessment model

The assessment follows the division of MOHs into two separate groups:

- mineral oil saturated hydrocarbons (MOSH)
- mineral oil aromatic hydrocarbons (MOAH)

For the definition of the groups see section 1.2 of the opinion.

The assessment follows further the steps of the risk assessment

1. Hazard identification and characterisation
2. Exposure assessment
3. Risk characterisation

For the hazard and exposure assessment the WG performed a screening to identify the uncertainties with highest impact on the output. Uncertainties with high priority are carried forward for the Expert knowledge elicitation (see Section 2) within sub groups of experts for the corresponding step. The individual judgments are reviewed and a consensus judgment is taken within the subgroups.

For simplification, the assessment was restricted to the age class of “Toddlers”, which shows generally highest exposure due to the unfavourable ratio of food intake to body weight and consequently highest risk.

Class	Age
Infants	< 12 months old
Toddlers	≥ 12 months to < 36 months old
Other children	≥ 36 months to < 10 years old
Adolescents	≥ 10 years to < 18 years old
Adults	≥ 18 years to < 65 years old
Elderly	≥ 65 years to < 75 years old
Very elderly	≥ 75 years old

Finally the uncertainty assessment on the risk characterisation, using hazard and exposure results of the expert elicitation, was done in the full working group by judging on the likelihood, that the “margin of exposure is below the acceptable level” for the age group of toddlers and was expressed considering the following scale:

Term	Probability of the outcome
Virtually certain	99-100% probability
Very likely	90-100% probability
Likely	66-100% probability
As likely as not	33-66% probability
Unlikely	0-33% probability
Very unlikely	0-10% probability
Exceptionally unlikely	0-1% probability

The assessment was then extended to all age groups.

H.1.3. EKE decision and confirmation

The EKE is needed to perform a quantitative uncertainty assessment for the main conclusions. The elicitation will be done within the WG following the semi-formal protocol.

H.2. EKE protocol

H.2.1. First EKE session: Hazard

H.2.1.1. Elicitation group (EG)

Role	Name
Scientific officer	Marco BINAGLIA
Elicitor	Olaf MOSBACH-SCHULZ
Recorder	
Expert profiles	
MOH hazard	Marco BINAGLIA
	Kevin CHIPMAN (Chair)
	Jan ALEXANDER
	Heather WALLACE
	Thomas TIETZ
Observers	
MOH exposure	Konrad GROB

H.2.1.2. Elicitation method and elicitor

The elicitation is performed using behavioural aggregation of individual answers of the elicitation group. The elicitation is facilitated by the EFSA internal EKE support group.

H.2.2. Hazard of MOSH

H.2.2.1. Evidence

The initial list of sources of uncertainty identified during the performance of the assessment was categorised using the default list of uncertainties compiled by the CONTAM Panel. The sources of uncertainty identified were subject to a prioritization exercise considering the magnitude of the uncertainty (i.e. the estimated change in the parameter that could occur if the uncertainty was solved) and its impact (i.e. the expected impact of the uncertainty in the overall assessment), as reported here below:

Uncertainty	Source of uncertainty	Direction of impact	Magnitude	Impact on assessment	Priority	Justification on priority score	
MOSH							
Uncertainty in the identification of key effects and target organs	1	Composition of MOSH material used in toxicological studies do not resemble the profiles found in food.	Unknown effects on direction	Moderate	Moderate	High	Some toxicologically relevant components may have been not properly tested
	1	Exact composition of the tested compounds is based on limited information	Unknown effects on direction	Large	Low	Low	Since the toxicological studies were conducted on mixtures (whole mixture approach), the impact is low despite the large magnitude of the uncertainty.
	2	Little information on absorption, metabolism and distribution of the different components	Unknown effects on direction	Moderate	Moderate	High	Presence of bioaccumulating components for which long term effects were not studied.

	3	Interspecies differences in ADME (F344 vs SD vs humans)	Unknown effects on direction	Moderate	Moderate	High	Irrespective of the higher accumulation of n-alkanes in F344 rats compared to humans and SD rats, possible over/underestimation of hazard (related to lower/higher accumulation of some components in humans)
	4	Presence of adverse effects not identified in F344 rats and other strains/species	Possible underestimation of hazard	Moderate	Moderate	High	Limited study duration and endpoints studied in F344. Limited info on other strains/species
	5	Human relevance of adverse effects observed in experimental animals	Possible underestimation of hazard	Moderate	High	High	Liver, spleen and MLN effects in F344 likely not relevant to humans. Poor information in other strains/species. Possible residual uncertainties that other relevant MOEs could be present (e.g. for effects in spleen)
	6	Uncertainty related to human observations	Possible underestimation of hazard	Moderate	Moderate	High	Unknown effects at levels observed in human tissues.
Uncertainty in the establishment of Reference Point	/	Uncertainty in the use of NOAEL instead of BMDL	Possible overestimation of hazard since the highest tested dose was selected	Moderate	Low	Low	Overall the uncertainty is low considering that no effects of relevant to humans were observed in F344 rats exposed to L-C25 at any tested dose.

The prioritised uncertainties were further discussed considering the available lines of evidence and the associated sources of uncertainty:

	Main sources for uncertainty identified (from prioritization table)	Lines of evidence	Associated sources uncertainty
1	Compositions of MOSH materials used in toxicological studies do not resemble the profiles found in food.	Several MOSH compositions (oils and waxes) tested in F344 rats gave consistent results (same effects and target organs, varying potency) EFSA study on broad mixture and fractions aimed to reflect the human exposure MOSH have batch to batch variation in composition (UVCB substances)	None of the compositions fully reflects the human exposure. MOSH entering certain foods (e.g. dairy products and other from the environment) could be enriched in components with higher bioaccumulation potential.
2	Little information on absorption, metabolism and distribution of the different components	Selective accumulation of certain fractions, tissue-specific Unknown fate of metabolites	Toxicity associated to long term accumulation not fully reflected in subchronic studies Long term effects of metabolites with bioaccumulation potential
3	Interspecies differences in ADME (F344 vs SD vs humans)	F344 more prone than humans and SD to accumulate n-alkanes in liver Different tissue distribution between F344 and humans: humans mainly distribute and accumulate MOSH in adipose tissue. Calculation of HED suggest similar behaviour of MOSH (other than n-alkanes) in F344 and human liver and spleen	Human accumulation of n-alkanes in liver could be present at higher doses than those from current dietary exposure. Long-term selective accumulation of certain MOSH not reflected in subchronic studies in F344 Evidence from weak human data (few subjects, unknown exposure)
4	Presence of adverse effects not identified in F344 rats and other strains/species	Effects in F344 follow a consistent pattern involving MLN (increased weight and granulomas), liver (increased weight and granulomas), spleen (increased weight), haematology (increased inflammatory response) Effects in other species (mainly SD) occurring at higher dose levels.	Key study on broad mixture and related subfractions examined restricted number of endpoints (mainly liver and spleen). Residual uncertainty of other adverse effects in F344 rats Information available only from a few studies. Uncertainty on possible presence of other adverse effects in test systems other than F344.
5	Human relevance of adverse effects observed in experimental animals	Effects in F344 follow a consistent pattern involving MLN (increased weight and granulomas), liver (increased weight and granulomas), spleen (increased weight), haematology (increased inflammatory response) Effects in MLN considered an adaptive (non-specific) response to low absorbable materials Effects in liver, spleen and haematological changes (including liver adenomas observed for ozokerite) of F344 rats related to n-alkane accumulation and precipitation in the liver. MO considered not relevant to humans.	Key study on broad mixture and related subfractions examined restricted number of endpoints (mainly liver and spleen). Residual uncertainty of other adverse effects in F344 rats MOSH found in human lymph nodes Possible relevance to human, although with lower sensitivity Possible presence of alternative MOA for effects in spleen
6	Uncertainty related to human observations	Use of white oils as placebo in clinical trials Use of white oils as laxatives well tolerated Lack of human epidemiological studies	Possible effects related to short term exposure to 1-5 g/person per day. Uncertainty related to the lack of properly designed studies (including an untreated control group). Unknowns in long term accumulation Unknown long-term effects at levels measured in human tissues

H.2.2.2. Evidence review

The following section summarizes the evidence/references reviewed and discussed during the EKE session. Intermediate results were obtained to structure the discussion and prepare for the final EKE question. The final review of the studies is documented in the scientific opinion.

Uncertainty 1: Profile of MOSHs in food versus in the experimental studies

Problem: In most of the studies used for the hazard assessment the profile of MOSH is different from that found in food.

Additional evidence: Comparison of hazard assessments using the same animal model, but different MOSH profiles, esp. "White oil/long chains", such as P70(H) or P100 (H) (low risk) and "S-C25" (high risk).

- Profiles in human tissues are measured, which may also differ from exposure via food
 - N-alkanes are not accumulated in human liver
- Many studies are on commercial products not reflecting the composition in food. One study is available on a broad mixture reflecting the composition of human exposure and related subfractions (Nygaard et al., 2019, see Opinion Section 3.1.2.2)
- S-C25: LOEL 23 mg/kg bw per day (increased spleen weight) (Nygaard et al., 2019)
- White oil/long chains: NOAEL 1200 mg/kg BW/d (Trimmer et al., 2004)
- L-C25 (Composition comparable to that observed in human liver): NOAEL 236 mg/kg BW/d (Nygaard et al., 2019)
 - Mixture of few substances

Mental model: The difference between study and human MOSH profile is captured by the differences of comparable studies with different MOSH profiles.

Assuming a study, for which this problem does not exist. How much would the result of the study differ from the current assessment, expressed as ratio "study without this problem/current assessment"?	Ratio	
	Low	High
	High risk	Low risk
Consensus	0.7	2
Expressed in NOAEL (Reference point 236 mg/kg BW/d)	160	480

Uncertainty 2: Effect of accumulation in several organs/tissues versus target organ of the study

Problem: The hazard assessment is using data on short-time accumulation in the liver and spleen and does not consider chronic exposure, only related to toxicokinetic, accumulation and redistribution from other organs.

Additional evidence: Compare the results of calculations done with different assumptions.

- The key study is a 90 day study (short time), long-term accumulation is not covered.
 - Trimmer et al (2004) study on white oils, the steady-state after 2 years is 1.5 times higher than the levels after 90 days, with high standard deviations/ no statistical difference.
- In rat liver, steady-state appears to be reached following subchronic exposure.

- Short-term studies are driven by non-accumulating MOSH. The composition of MOSH in the organism is expected to vary over time, with an enrichment of the components with higher accumulation potential, which are a small proportion of the overall MOSH.

Mental model: A chronic study is done, change with respect to toxicokinetics, accumulation effect.

The effect of accumulation and re-distribution is captured by the different assumptions.

Assuming a study, for which this problem doesn't exist. How much would the result of the study differ from the current assessment, expressed as ratio "study without this problem/current assessment"?	Ratio	
	Low	High
	High risk	Low risk
Consensus	0.8	2
Expressed as NOEL (Reference point 236 mg/kg BW/d)	190	480

Uncertainty 3: Differences of accumulation in humans versus animal model in studies

Problem: F344 rats have a specific accumulation behaviour, accumulating more n-alkanes in liver, and relatively less in the adipose tissue (compared to SD rats and humans)

Additional evidence:

- Based on estimation of human equivalent doses (HED), the elimination rate in human liver, spleen and adipose tissue is slower than in rats. In particular in the human adipose tissue chronic accumulation of MOSH is observed (see Section 3.1.1.2 and Appendix E of the opinion for detailed discussion)
- HED calculations show in liver and a factor of 4, spleen about 10, adipose tissue more than 100 (see Scientific Opinion for additional details)
- Non-linearity of elimination rate over time due to different MOSH profiles

Mental model:

Which additional factor is needed to adapt the standard extrapolation factor "Animal to humans"? (Take 1 divided by this factor)

Assuming a study, for which this problem doesn't exist. How much would the result of this study differ from the current assessment, expressed as adapted extrapolation factor to cover this uncertainty?	Adapted extrapolation factor			
	from		to	
		(calculated in comparison to 4)		(calculated in comparison to 4)
Consensus	4	(1)	20	(5)

The ideal study is a sub-chronic study with humans: What is the ratio of NOEL(human)/NOEL(F344), with respect to toxicokinetic, accumulation?

Transformation to the ratio:

Assuming a study, for which this problem doesn't exist. How much would the result of this study differ from the current assessment, expressed as ratio "study without this problem/current assessment"?	Ratio	
	Low	High
Consensus (transformed)	0.2	1
Expressed as NOEL (Reference point 236 mg/kg BW/d)	48	240

Uncertainty 4: Reduced endpoints in existing studies

Problem: Most studies were restricted to liver, spleen, MLN effects / a few studies on other endpoints

Additional evidence: Stratify the analysis on older / newer (sub-chronic) studies and the study of Trimmer et al. (2004)

- Reproduction, developmental endpoints, neurotoxicity, immune-toxicity histology of many tissues, blood parameter missing
- For some MOHs, e.g. waxes, modern studies exist no additional endpoints are found:
 - List of studies

Mental model:

Assuming a study, for which this problem doesn't exist. How much would the result of this study differ from the current assessment, expressed as ratio "study without this problem/current assessment"?	Ratio	
	Low	High
Consensus	0.4	2
Expressed as NOAEL (Reference point 236 mg/kg BW/d)	96	480

Uncertainty 5: Exclusion of some endpoints in animal studies

Problem: Some effects in the animal model were excluded, e.g. spleen weight, MLN

Additional evidence: Redo the assessment without exclusion of some effects.

- Effect on spleen weight observed in several studies, assumed as secondary effect of immune reaction
 - In the SC25 study the LOEL was 23mg/kg BW per day
- Effect on MLN (increased weight associated with increased incidence of granulomas) is shown in rats, but considered of low biological relevance
 - Effects already observed for 20mg/kg BW per day in oils, 2 mg/kg BW per day for waxes

Mental model: The effect of exclusion (of some endpoints) can be estimated from the comparison

Assuming a study, for which this problem doesn't exist. How much would the result of the this study differ from the current assessment, expressed as ratio "study without this problem (Spleen weight, Lymph nodes are relevant)/current assessment"?	Ratio	
	Low	High
Consensus	0.01	Not done
Expressed as NOAEL (Reference point 236 mg/kg BW/d)	2.4	

Uncertainty 6: Use of MOSHs as laxative and other human observations

Problem: White oils (MOSH) are intentionally used as laxatives. The corresponding doses are out of the range of the animal model. In a series of publication assessing the use of paraffin oils as placebo in clinical trials, increases in markers associated with atherosclerosis and inflammatory response were observed.

Additional evidence: Estimate the corresponding dose of the use.

Mental model: The effect will be between "no additional effect" and the "maximum effect", which cannot be attributed to a possible misuse.

These uncertainties will be discussed in a narrative way in the opinion, as special use of MOSH

H.2.2.3. Scenario

Please assume the perfect study:

- Composition of MOSH material corresponds to the profile in food, expressed in the molecular mass range and composition
- Chronic study duration covers absorption, metabolism and distribution of the different components, esp. bioaccumulation (not covered by the extrapolation factor of 2 "short → long duration")
- Species used in the study reflect the accumulation in humans (not covered by the extrapolation factor of 4 "animals → humans")
- Effects reported are relevant to humans (correct endpoint), including effects not considered in the animal systems

H.2.2.4. EKE questions

Topic	Description
Parameter	Relative uncertainty of hazard estimate of MOSH
Strata	MOSH
Question	Assuming a perfect study according to the scenario is performed. How much would the result of the perfect study differ from the current assessment, expressed as ratio "perfect/current"?
Unit	[-] / < 1 increased risk / > 1 decreased risk
Operationalisation	Perform the perfect study and report the result. The ratio between the result of the perfect study divided by the current assessment is the answer.

H.2.2.5. Summary

Assuming a study, for which this problem doesn't exist. How much would the result of the study differ from the current assessment, expressed as ratio "study without this problem/current assessment"?	Low	High
Uncertainty 1: Effect of different profile of MOSHs in food versus in the selected study	0.7	2
Uncertainty 2: Effect of sub-chronic instead chronic study, with respect to toxico-kinetic, accumulation	0.8	2
Uncertainty 3: Effect of slower accumulation in humans versus F344 rats in the selected study	0.2	1
Uncertainty 4: Effect of reduced set of endpoints in the selected study	0.4	2
Uncertainty 5: Effect of de-selected endpoint (spleen weight, lymph nodes) in the selected study (Question, if effects are adverse)	0.01	

Assuming a perfect study according to the scenario is performed. How much would the result of the perfect study differ from the current assessment, expressed as ratio "perfect NOAEL/current NOAEL", which is not covered by the standard extrapolation factors (Sub/chronic=2; rats/human=10 (incl. toxico-kinetic=4); intra-human=10)?

(actual used NOAEL is 236mg/kg BW/d, L-C25 Study).

Assuming a perfect study according to the scenario is performed. How much would the result of the perfect study differ from the current assessment, expressed as ratio "perfect NOAEL/current NOAEL", which is not covered by the standard extrapolation factors?					
	L	Q1	M	Q3	H
Consensus	0.05	0.2	0.33	0.8	2
Expressed as NOAEL (Reference point 236 mg/kg BW/d)	12	48	80	192	480

Alternative framing of the question:

It should be noted, that the elicitation considers only the specific uncertainties, which are not yet covered by the default extrapolation factor. To enable the experts for this judgement, the question was also reframed to "the range of the extrapolation factor, which covers standard and specific uncertainties". The answer of the EKE question can be calculated by standard factor/total factor.

Which range of extrapolation factors (instead of the default of 200) should be used to cover all uncertainties?					
	L	Q1	M	Q3	H
Consensus	100				4000

H.2.2.6. Result report

Please see the result table for details. The results used in the final assessment are reported in the scientific opinion.

H.2.2.7. Process documentation

The elicitation was done in steps:

1. The experts/working group were identifying relevant uncertainties using the standard checklist
2. In a preparatory meeting the experts identified additional evidence, which were used to quantify the effect (bias) of the relevant uncertainties on the hazard estimate
3. In the EKE meeting on 27th Sep 2022 the experts judging the effect of each relevant uncertainty in the hazard assessment of MOSH separately, by a low and high factor scenario.
4. Finally the total uncertainty of the hazard assessment of MOSH was performed by a semi-formal EKE with the quartile method. A uncertainty distribution was fitted to the EKE results.
5. In the EKE meeting on 26th October 2022 points 3 and 4 were repeated for MOAHs. To avoid confusions the elicitation question was re-framed by the "ratio of risk" shown as "risk assessed in a perfect study/risk assessed in the current assessment". This is the reciprocal to the ratio of the reference doses.

H.2.2.8. Discussions

The reasoning is documented in the evidence review and summarised in the result table.

EKE results

Overview of the results of the Expert Knowledge Elicitation (Hazard Assessment MOSH)															
Parameter	Uncertainty factor of the hazard assessment MOSH														
Stratification	Mineral Oil Saturated Hydrocarbons (MOSH)														
Question	Assuming a perfect study according to the scenario is performed. How much would the result of the perfect study differ from the current assessment, expressed as ratio "perfect NOAEL/current NOAEL", which is not covered by the standard extrapolation factors?														
Unit	[-] expressed as factors: 1/X or X														
Results	P1%	P2.5%	P5%	P10%	P16.7%	P25%	P33.3%	P50%	P66.7%	P75%	P83.3%	P90%	P95%	P97.5%	P99%
EKE consensus	0.05					0.20		0.33		0.80					2.00
EKE results: Ratio	0.05	0.05	0.06	0.08	0.12	0.17	0.23	0.39	0.60	0.75	0.96	1.19	1.48	1.72	2.00
NOAEL (perfect study) [mg/kg BW/d] Reference: 236	11.8	12.7	14.8	19.7	27.9	40.1	54.5	91.1	143	178	226	281	348	406	472
	P99%	P97.5%	P95%	P90%	P83.3%	P75%	P66.7%	P50%	P33.3%	P25%	P16.7%	P10%	P5%	P2.5%	P1%
Multiplier to the existing assessment factor	20	19	16	12	8.5	5.9	4.3	2.6	1.7	1.3	1.0	0.84	0.68	0.58	0.50
Assessment factor Reference: 200	4001	3702	3199	2391	1693	1178	866	518	331	265	209	168	136	116	100
Fitted distribution (Ratio)	BetaGeneral(0.77526,4.3225,0.0482,3.2)														

Figure (a): Comparison of elicited and fitted values / density function to describe the remaining uncertainties of the parameter	Figure (b): Cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the likelihood of the parameter
Summary of the evidence used for the evaluation	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The assessment bases mainly on a sub-chronic study of LC25 – key study - with a NOAEL of 236 mg/kg BW/d and a mixture of industrial MOSHs, minimising n-alkanes Further studies were identified on single MOHs, mixtures with alkanes, effects on the spleen weight and lymph nodes Levels in different organs were analysed showing the liver as main human target organ Measurements in human tissue show the possible accumulation behaviour 	
Main uncertainties	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The effect of the difference of the MOSH profile in human food compared to the MOSH profile in the key study is uncertain. This may over- or underestimate the hazard. The limitations caused by using a sub-chronic key study instead of a chronic study are uncertain. This may over- or underestimate the hazard. The effect of slower elimination of persistent MOSHs in humans than in F344 rats, as in the key study, is uncertain. This uncertainty underestimates the hazard and may lead to a high bias. The limitations caused by the absence of newer studies with protocols according to the current standards are uncertain. This may over- or underestimate the hazard. The correctness of classifying some endpoints as without adverse effects is unclear. This uncertainty may underestimate the hazard. 	
Reasoning for a scenario which would lead to a reasonable high ratio	The judgement on the upper limit considers that <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The key study identified the highest dose as NOAEL. Higher doses in the perfect study may also show no effect.
Reasoning for a scenario which would lead to a reasonable low ratio	The judgement on the lower limit considers that <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The MOSH profile in food may contain higher proportions of long accumulating MOSH The semi-chronic study is not covering long accumulation effects The elimination rate in humans is slower than in the animal model, esp. non-linear over time (highly likely) Modern studies could identify additional endpoints (likely) Excluded endpoints could be relevant (less likely)
Fair estimate as judgement on the weighted evidence	The judgement on the median considers that <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Slower elimination rate/ higher accumulation in humans compared to the animal model is likely, which indicate a lower median value/ right skewed distribution for the estimated risk Some endpoints are not covered by the evaluated studies
Precision of the judgement as description of remaining uncertainties	The judgement on the interquartile range considers that <ul style="list-style-type: none"> High uncertainty for factors below the median, as many uncertainties point to lower factors / higher risk Low uncertainty for factors above the median, due to dose selection of the key study
Experts	Marco BINAGLIA, Kevin CHIPMAN, Jan ALEXANDER, Thomas TIETZ, Heather WALLACE (participating initially),
Observer	Konrad GROB
Facilitator / Reporter	Olaf MOSBACH-SCHULZ
Date and place of the EKE	The EKE (semi-formal protocol) was done on the 27 th September 2022 in a virtual meeting

1 **H.2.3. Hazard of MOAH**

2 **H.2.3.1. Evidence**

3 The following uncertainties were identified and prioritised as described in Section 2.2 of this
 4 document:

Uncertainty	Sources of uncertainty	Direction of impact	Magnitude	Impact on assessment	Priority	Justification on priority score	
MOAH							
Uncertainty in the identification of key effects and target organs	1	Composition of MOH/MOAH material used in toxicological studies do not resemble the profiles found in food.	Unknown effects on direction	High	High	High	Some toxicologically relevant components may have been not properly tested.
	/	Exact composition of the tested compounds is based on limited information	Unknown effects on direction	Large	Low	Low	Since the toxicological studies were conducted on mixtures (whole mixture approach), the impact is low despite the large magnitude of the uncertainty.
	2	Incomplete dataset for the oral toxicity other than reprotoxicity	Underestimation of hazards	High	Moderate	High	Underestimation of non-neoplastic effects.
	/	Uncertainty on the sensitivity of the genotoxicity testing	Underestimation of hazards	Moderate	Low	Low	Possible underestimation for the presence of genotoxic constituents in MOAH due testing only as a mixture (dilution). No impact on the overall hazard identification
	/	Lack of oral carcinogenicity data of MOAH	Unknown effects on direction	Moderate	Low	Low	Possible higher/lower potency compared to dermal exposure. Eventually low impact since the RP is based on PAHs (ref. to N. 3).
	/	No human observation available	Unknown effects on direction	Large	Low	Low	Large magnitude but no direct impact on the assessment since the assessment is only based on animal data.
Uncertainty in the establishment of Reference Point	3	Use of surrogate RP from the PAH assessment	Overestimation of neoplastic hazards	Moderate	Moderate	High	Unknown oral carcinogenic potency of 3-7 ring MOAH vs the PAHs used in the long-term study (EFSA, 2008). Likely overall an overestimation of the hazard.
	/	BMDL10s for the PAHs derived following an outdated BMD approach	Unknown effects on direction.	Low	Low	Low	Considering the MOE approach for genotoxic and carcinogenic substances, the update of the BMD calculation using the most recent guidance is not expected to have a large impact on the overall assessment.

5

6 The prioritised uncertainties were further discussed considering the available lines of evidence and the
 7 associated sources of uncertainty:

	Main sources of uncertainty identified (from prioritization table)	Lines of evidence	Associated sources uncertainty
1	Composition of MOH/MOAH material used in toxicological studies do not resemble the profiles found in food.	The few studies available are on MOAH-containing unrefined MOH (e.g. DAE) or refined MOH compositions. MOH have batch to batch variation in composition (UVCB) MOH refinement is controlled by means of IP 346 method (DMSO extraction) to identify genotoxic and carcinogenic MOAH.	Unknown relevance of test materials in relation to the MOAH fraction present in food. Uncertainty in the sensitivity of the method. Possible underestimation of hazard (for products passing the IP 346 test)
2	Incomplete dataset for the oral toxicity other than Reproduction toxicity	Limited information suggests a low toxicity of MOH passing the IP 346 tests General conservativeness of the approach used for genotoxic and carcinogenic substances could be sufficient to protect against unidentified non-neoplastic effects	Lack of full characterization of oral toxicity, possible underestimation of the non-neoplastic hazards
3	Use of surrogate RP from the PAH assessment	Noting few exceptions, alkylated polycyclic MOAH with 3 or more rings are unlikely to be more potent oral carcinogens than non-alkylated PAHs.	General uncertainty in read across between PAHs and 3-7 ring MOAH.

8

9 H.2.3.2. Evidence review

10 The following section summarizes the evidence/references reviewed and discussed during the EKE
 11 session. Intermediate results were obtained to structure the discussion and prepare for the final EKE
 12 question. The final review of the studies is documented in the scientific opinion.

13

14 **Uncertainty 1: Profile of MOAH in food versus the material used in experimental** 15 **studies on MOH/PAH**

16

Assuming a study, for which this problem doesn't exist. How much would the result of the this study differ from the current assessment, expressed as ratio in risk "study without this problem/current assessment"?	Ratio	
	Low	High
Consensus	0.005	0.2

17

- 18 • No information on profiles of MOAH in food or experiments, because its complexity and diversity
- 19 • Small differences in the structure may show different effects. No multiple studies, which could
 20 be used for quantification
- 21 • Qualitative evidence is coming from skin studies, comparison with PAH.
- 22 • The reference point used is coming from PAH, which are a fraction of MOAH, with oral data
- 23 • For genotoxicity is risk yes/no; only parts of MOAH are genotoxic
- 24 • For genotoxic effects the carcinogenic potency is of interest, which is for MOAH likely lower
 25 than for PAH (worst case)
- 26 • Initiator/promoter problem is similar for MOAH as for PAHs.
- 27 • Profile in food is purified for carcinogenic substances, max 10% carcinogenic components, all
 28 with likely lower potency than PAHs

29 **Uncertainty 2: Effect of incorrect exposure pathway**

30 This uncertainty is handled together with Uncertainty 1 and 3.

31 **Uncertainty 3: Limitation of the assessment regarding endpoints other than** 32 **genotoxicity**

33 **Problem:** Main fraction of MOAH is not similar PAH, esp. likely not genotoxic, but other chronic effects
 34 are possible

35 **Additional evidence:**

36 **Mental model:** Assume a likely profile, e.g. 10% 'like PAHs', 90% 'not like PAHs'.

37

Assuming a study, for which this problem doesn't exist. How much would the result of this study differ from the current assessment, expressed as ratio of risks "study without this problem/current assessment"?	Ratio	
	Low	High
Consensus	1	1.5

38

- 39 • Sub-chronic, chronic studies are missing, because of the focus on genotoxic effects/fraction
- 40 • Alternative effects are likely, but these are of less concern
- 41 • Small fraction with high toxicity against large fraction with possible low toxicity

42

43 **H.2.3.3. Scenario**

44 Please assume the perfect study:

- 45 • Composition of MOAH material corresponds to the profile in food
- 46 • No use of a substitute: PAH instead of MOAH
- 47 • All effects, esp. non-neoplastic, are correctly considered

48 Please assume the perfect study:

- 49 • MOAH material is extracted from a representative diet (correct, but unknown profile)
- 50 • Study protocol includes all possible effects (incl. genotoxic, carcinogenic, chronic etc)

51

52 **H.2.3.4. EKE questions**

Topic	Description
Parameter	Relative uncertainty of hazard estimate of MOAH
Strata	MOAH
Question	Assuming a perfect study according to the scenario is performed. How much would the risk assessed in the perfect study differ from the risk assessed in the current study, expressed as ratio of risks "perfect study/current study"? This is the reciprocal of the ratio of reference doses.
Unit	[-] / >1 increased risk / < 1 decreased risk (aligned framing)
Operationalisation	Perform the perfect study and report the result. The ratio between the result of the perfect study divided by the current assessment is the answer.

53

54

55

H.2.3.5. Summary:

Assuming a study, for which this problem doesn't exist. How much would the result of the this study differ from the current assessment, expressed as ratio "study without this problem/current assessment"?	Low	High
Uncertainty 1: Profile of MOAH in food versus in the used experimental studies on PAH	0.005	0.2
Uncertainty 3: Limitation of the assessment regarding endpoints other than genotoxicity	1	1.5

56

57 Because of the domination of uncertainty 1 and small number of relevant uncertainties, the range for
58 the overall uncertainty was calculated as worst case.

Assuming a study, for which this problem does not exist. How much would the result of the study differ from the current assessment, expressed as ratio of risks "study without this problem/current assessment"?					
	L	Q1	M	Q3	H
Consensus	0.005	0.012	0.02	0.08	0.3

59

60

H.2.3.6. Result report

61 The following section summarizes the evidence/references reviewed and discussed during the EKE
62 session. Intermediate results were obtained to structure the discussion and prepare for the final EKE
63 question. The final review of the studies is documented in the scientific opinion.

64

H.2.3.7. Process documentation

65 The elicitation process on MOSH was also applied for MOAH.

66

H.2.3.8. Discussions

67 The reasoning is documented in the evidence review and summarised in the result table.

68

69 **EKE results**

Overview of the results of the Expert Knowledge Elicitation (Hazard Assessment MOAH)															
Parameter	Uncertainty factor of the hazard assessment MOAH														
Stratification	Mineral Oil Aromatic Hydrocarbons (MOAH)														
Question	Assuming a perfect study according to the scenario is performed. How much would the result of the perfect study differ from the current assessment, expressed as ratio of risks "study without this problem/current assessment", which is not covered by the standard extrapolation factors? (For fitting the factor is converted to the reciprocal ratio of the reference dose of the optimal experiment and the reference dose in the assessment)														
Unit	[-] expressed as factors: 1/X or X														
Results	P1%	P2.5%	P5%	P10%	P16.7 %	P25%	P33.3 %	P50%	P66.7 %	P75%	P83.3 %	P90%	P95%	P97.5 %	P99%
EKE consensus Risk ratio	0.005					0.012		0.02		0.08					0.3
	P99%	P97.5%	P95%	P90%	P83.3%	P75%	P66.7%	P50%	P33.3%	P25%	P16.7%	P10%	P5%	P2.5%	P1%
EKE consensus expressed as ratio of reference doses	200					83.33		50		12.5					3.33
EKE final result on the ratio of reference doses	199.9	185.3	167.8	142.3	116.9	92.2	72.4	42.4	21.7	14.2	8.58	5.42	3.91	3.47	3.32
RefVal (perfect study) [mg/kg BW/d] Reference: 0.49	98.0	90.8	82.2	69.7	57.3	45.2	35.5	20.8	10.6	6.96	4.20	2.66	1.92	1.70	1.63
Fitted distribution (Ratio Risk)	BetaGeneral(0.56842,1.6381,3.28,220)														

70

71

72

Summary of the evidence used for the evaluation	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The assessment bases mainly on the EFSA risk assessment on PAH 	
Main uncertainties	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The MOAH profile in food differs from the PAH profile used in the risk assessment Only parts of the of the MOAHs are genotoxic, difficult to classify from their structure (likely, important) Missing studies with other endpoints, than genotoxicity, unclear other toxic effects (less important) 	
Reasoning for a scenario which would lead to a reasonable high ratio	The judgement on the upper limit considers that <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Larger proportion of MOAHs are (similar to) PAHs Alternative effects are important
Reasoning for a scenario which would lead to a reasonable low ratio	The judgement on the lower limit considers that <ul style="list-style-type: none"> MOAHs in food are purified from genotoxic/carcinogenic components, low proportion of carcinogenic MOAHs Large proportion of MOAHs are degraded, not incorporated
Fair estimate as judgement on the weighted evidence	The judgement on the median considers that <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The current assessment overestimates the risks Only small proportion 1% to 10% of MOAHs are similar to PAHs
Precision of the judgement as description of remaining uncertainties	The judgement on the interquartile range considers that <ul style="list-style-type: none"> High uncertainty on factors below the median Moderate uncertainty on factors above the median (right skewed distribution)
Experts	Marco BINAGLIA, Kevin CHIPMAN, Jan ALEXANDER, Heather WALLACE
Observer	EC
Facilitator / Reporter	Olaf MOSBACH-SCHULZ
Date and place of the EKE	The EKE (semi-formal protocol) was done on the 26 th October 2022 in a virtual meeting

73

74 **H.2.4. Second EKE session: Exposure**

75 **H.2.4.1. Elicitation group**

Role	Name
Scientific officer	Marco BINAGLIA
Elicitor	Olaf MOSBACH-SCHULZ
Recorder	Marco BINAGLIA
Expert profile	
MOH exposure	José Ángel GÓMEZ RUIZ
	Christophe GOLDBECK
	Konrad GROB
	Annette PETERSEN
Observers	
MOH hazard	Kevin CHIPMAN (Chair)
	Heather WALLACE

76

77 **H.2.4.2. Elicitation method**

78 The elicitation is performed using behavioural aggregation of individual answers of the elicitation group.

79 The elicitation is facilitated by the EFSA internal EKE support group.

80

81 **H.2.5. Exposure to MOSH**

82 **H.2.5.1. Evidence**

83 The uncertainties identified in the list here below were highly ranked for relevance in the risk
 84 assessment.

OCCURRENCE AND EXPOSURE ASSESSMENT (MOAH and MOSH)		
	Description of uncertainty	Impact on the exposure assessment? 1 – minor 2 – intermediate 3 – high
Occurrence data	Uncertainty due to the performance (e.g. specificity for the target compounds, sample preparation) of the analytical methods?	For both MOSH and MOAH, in particular the latter, the incomplete removal of certain interferences might impact the analytical results. This can highly depend on the type of food matrix under analysis. Some treatments to remove interferences may also cause losses of MOSH and MOAH. Interpretation of the chromatograms Impact on MOSH ---2 Impact on MOAH --- 3
	Analytical capability of the method - sensitivity (e.g. LOQ, LOD).	The decrease in limits of detection/quantification implies a higher impact of analytical interferences on the analytical measurements. Diverse approaches used to derive and report the left-censoring limits Impact on MOSH ---2 Impact on MOAH --- 3

	<p>Uncertainty in the information on processing, e.g. processing prior to the analysis of the samples. Possible effect of industrial processing and/or household preparation on the chemical concentrations.</p>	<p>For herbal/tea infusions a low transfer from powder to drink is expected. There could be evaporation during cooking (e.g. from noodles/rice or edible oils (refined oils have already lost volatile fraction))</p> <p>Impact on MOSH -- 1 Impact on MOAH --- 1</p>
	<p>Use of models for imputing occurrence levels to left-censored (below LOD or LOQ) analytical results, e.g. lower bound/upper bound scenarios</p>	<p>The left-censored data accounted for 74.3% of all the data (54,395 analytical results). They were particularly high for MOAH, where for the four individual C-fractions approximately 93% of the results were reported either as below the LOD or below the LOQ. The exposure is likely to be underestimated with the LB approach and overestimated with the UB approach.</p> <p>Impact on MOSH -- 1 Impact on MOAH --- 2</p>
	<p>Variation in MOH levels due to time spent in contact with FCM before being consumed</p>	<p>Depending on the type of food and food contact material, storage time (in shelves, at home) might increase the levels of some MOH in the food (from FCM to the food matrix)</p> <p>Impact on MOSH -- 1 Impact on MOAH --- 1</p>
	<p>Representativeness of the data</p>	<p>Concentrations not representing Eastern countries with possible higher MOSH concentrations than those used as mean concentrations.</p> <p>Impact on MOSH -- 1 Impact on MOAH --- 1</p>
<p>Dietary exposure</p>	<p>Sources of exposure other than dietary - how much important is dietary exposure to the total</p>	<p>For MOSH, potential high contribution from lipsticks and baby cosmetics (oral uptake) and cosmetics (dermal absorption).</p> <p>For MOAH, possible additional professional and occupational exposure.</p> <p>Impact on MOSH -- 3 Impact on MOAH --- 1-2</p>

85

86 Uncertainties and limitations were also identified related to the use of the EFSA Comprehensive Food
 87 Consumption Database (see Appendix G). The main uncertainties have been described by EFSA (EFSA,
 88 2011a) and generally relate to the use of different dietary survey methodologies, standard portion sizes,
 89 representativeness of samples included in surveys, or to the inclusion of consumption surveys covering
 90 only few days to estimate high percentiles of chronic exposure. These uncertainties are common to
 91 dietary chronic exposure assessments performed using the Comprehensive Database, and have the
 92 potential to cause either an over- or under-estimation of the exposure. The uncertainties affecting the
 93 food consumption data were not specific for the MOAH and MOSH exposure assessment. They are
 94 'standard uncertainties' across all opinions and were considered to have low priority. It is generally
 95 accepted that the estimates from the Comprehensive Database are generally considered to be fit-for-
 96 purpose, provided there are no non-standard uncertainties, as it is the case for MOAH and MOSH.

97 H.2.5.2. Evidence review

98 Uncertainty: Simplified exposure model for toddlers

99 **Problem:** The effect of missing or sparse occurrence data on MOSH, limitations with the analytical
 100 methods used for its detection, and the effect of processing should be explored.

101 Additional evidence:

102 To allow the experts to analyse the uncertainties connected to the exposure model a simplified version
 103 was constructed, which estimates the exposure through the full diet of an average European toddler.
 104 The food categories were limited to the FoodEx level 2. As intake the mean and 95th percentile of the
 105 observations in all studies was taken.

106 The simplified model was evaluated with the observations used in the exposure assessment.

107 Mental model:

108 Furthermore, the experts were asked to review the observed contaminations and map these also on the
 109 food categories of the complete diet regarding following uncertainties:

- 110 • Effect of limitations of the analytical methods used for detection, e.g. determination of the LOD
 111 for the sum of several MOHs
- 112 • Impute observations below the LOQ/LOD using additional evidence on the presence of
 113 contaminations
- 114 • Extrapolate from food categories with observations to categories without observations using
 115 additional information on the food categories, e.g. the fat content

116 For each food category a lower and upper limit, and a median estimate was judged. The latter describes
 117 an average contamination, which should neither over- nor underestimate the true contamination. The
 118 exposure is summed for the complete diet. The results are documented in a separate file.

119 To describe the uncertainties the exposure via the complete diet (mental model) is compared with the
 120 result (middle bound) of the simplified model restricted to the observations of the exposure analysis
 121 (current analysis). Finally the ratio between the exposure of the complete model and the current analysis
 122 is taken as measure of the full uncertainties.

123 This exercise indicates that for the mean consumer (average European toddler) the exposure of MOSH
 124 via the complete diet is 9% higher (factor 1.09) than calculated in the current exposure analysis with
 125 a range from "lower bound" 15% less (factor 0.85) to "upper bound" 32% more (factor 1.32). The
 126 exposure to MOSH of the high consumer (P95) toddler is 8% higher (factor 1.08) than calculated in
 127 the current exposure analysis with a range from "lower bound" 16% less (factor 0.84) to "upper
 128 bound" 31% more (factor 1.31).

129 Additional exposure via breastfeeding is not included in the uncertainty analysis and discussed
 130 separately in the opinion.

131

132 H.2.5.3. Scenario

133 Please assume the study to address the needs of the exposure assessment:

- 134 • Full diet of toddlers is evaluated;
 - 135 ○ Breastfeeding is excluded from the exposure assessment and will be handled
 136 separately;
 - 137 ○ All non-food pathways are excluded;
- 138 • Evaluation is done with the processed food;
- 139 • Large, representative European Survey on food consumption and contamination;
- 140 • Contaminations are measured with a LOD low enough to captured all contamination / complete
 141 data (no observations below LOQ unless no contamination is present);

- 142 • Uncertainties related to the dietary survey methodology are not considered in the uncertainty
 143 assessment.

144 Regarding the existing assessment:

- 145 • In the existing assessment the middle between LB and UB is calculated for each survey. The
 146 median of all European survey is used as "Point of departure" for the comparison;
- 147 • The exposure estimate in the current assessment is: 0.066 mg/kg MOSH for the mean toddler
 148 and 0.105 mg/kg MOSH for the P95 toddler expressed as the middle value between LB and UB
 149 and median across all dietary surveys in the comprehensive database.

150

151 H.2.5.4. EKE questions

Topic	Description
Parameter	Exposure of toddlers to MOSH
Strata	Age class: Toddlers Substances: MOSH
Question	In comparison to the existing estimated exposure of toddlers to MOSH (expressed as middle value between LB and UB) and the median exposure calculated across all European surveys, what is the relative change of the estimated exposure after assuming no uncertainty in the survey methodology (large, representative European Survey on food consumption and contamination) and complete measurements (no data below LOQ, except uncontaminated samples (real zeros))?
Unit	[-], Factor X or 1/X
Operationalisation	The perfect measurements are included in the assessment and the change is observed. The ratio of changed and existing exposure assessment is the answer.

152

153 H.2.5.5. Discussions and EKE consensus

154 The following table summarizes the main uncertainties discussed during the EKE session. Additionally
 155 the results of the uncertainty screening and the calculations of the simplified model were used for the
 156 judgement on the EKE questions to cover the overall uncertainties.

157

Uncertainty	Scenario for lower exposure (low factor)	Scenario for higher exposure (high factor)	Remarks
Regional differences in concentrations		Concentrations not representing Eastern countries with possible higher MOSH concentrations than those used as mean concentrations	
Laboratory practise in analysing MOSH	Modern data represent standard practise, Older data show higher values which may indicate an overestimation due to the presence of impurities	Some methods may have problems to detect some MOSH due to "not good practise", in particular, older measurements	
Reporting of results not being harmonized among data providers. Detection of single substances instead of the complete signal	When analysing individual fractions underestimation of the concentration (not considering the whole hump).	At the UB, summing LOQs from individual fractions for estimations can result in overestimation of the levels.	Less problematic on non-fatty food (e.g. grains)

158

159

In comparison to the existing estimated exposure of toddlers to MOSH, what is the relative change of the estimated exposure after assuming no uncertainty in survey methodology, and complete measurements?

	L	Q1	M	Q3	H
Consensus	0.9	1.05	1.1	1.15	1.2

160

161 **H.2.5.6. Result report**

162 Please see the result table for details. The results used in the final assessment are reported in the
 163 scientific opinion.

164 **H.2.5.7. Process documentation**

165 The elicitation was done in steps:

- 166 1. The experts/working group were identifying relevant uncertainties using the
 167 standard checklist
- 168 2. In a preparatory meeting the experts identified additional evidence, which were
 169 used to fill the simplified model on the exposure via the complete diet.
- 170 3. In the EKE meeting on 29th November 2022 the experts judged on the total
 171 uncertainty of the exposure assessment by a semi-formal EKE with the quartile
 172 method. A uncertainty distribution was fitted to the EKE results.

173 **H.2.5.8. Discussions**

174 The reasoning is documented in the evidence review and summarised in the result table.

175

176 **EKE results**

Overview of the results of the Expert Knowledge Elicitation (Exposure Assessment MOSH)															
Parameter	Exposure of toddlers to MOSH														
Stratification	Age class: Toddlers / Substances: MOSH														
Question	In comparison to the existing estimated exposure of toddlers to MOSH (expressed as middle value between LB and UB) and the median exposure calculated across all European surveys, what is the relative change of the estimated exposure after assuming no uncertainty in survey methodology (large, representative European Survey on food consumption and contamination) and complete measurements (no data below LOQ, except uncontaminated samples (real zeros))?														
Unit	[-]														
Results	P1%	P2.5%	P5%	P10%	P16.7%	P25%	P33.3%	P50%	P66.7%	P75%	P83.3%	P90%	P95%	P97.5%	P99%
EKE consensus	0.90					1.05		1.10		1.15					1.20
EKE results: Ratio	0.905	0.935	0.962	0.994	1.02	1.05	1.07	1.10	1.13	1.15	1.16	1.18	1.19	1.20	1.21
Fitted distribution	BetaGeneral(5.6864,2.104,0.75,1.22)														

177

Summary of the evidence used for the evaluation	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The assessment is based on the European occurrence data on MOSH, and the food consumption of toddlers in the EFSA database A mean and P95 diet of European toddlers was constructed (FoodEx2 level 3) and evaluated using a simplified exposure model The evidences of contamination for each food category in the diet were reviewed. Data gaps were filled by appropriate extrapolation from similar food categories as needed. 	
Main uncertainties	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The effect of high levels of left censored data (e.g. excluded from the exposure assessment), few or missing observations is unclear The occurrence data may not be representative for whole European population, e.g. fewer data from Eastern Europe. Some occurrence data are provided from industry, less experienced laboratories, and not following the current measurement analytical standards, and /or analysing foods from more recent sampling years. Some measurements were done on individual substances and later combined to a value for the group, which increases the possible detection level 	
Reasoning for a scenario which would lead to a reasonable high ratio	<p>The judgement on the upper limit considers that</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Left-censored occurrence data represent contamination close to the detection/quantification level Food categories in the toddlers diet without occurrence data will contribute to the intake Regions (e.g. Eastern Europe) underrepresented in the database of occurrence data might be exposed to higher MOSH levels than those used as representative of the levels in the European market (mean across all countries) Measurements not following the current analytical standards for MOSH analysis might show lower concentrations Measurements on single compounds (later combined) underestimate the concentration, e.g. in fatty food
Reasoning for a scenario which would lead to a reasonable low ratio	<p>The judgement on the lower limit considers that</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Food categories with high level of left-censored data, with few or none measurements are not contaminated Current exposure may be lower than in the past
Fair estimate as judgement on the weighted evidence	<p>The judgement on the median considers that</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Food categories with few/no measurements show contaminations as similar categories, or “background contaminations” A median factor of 1.10 indicates that the current exposure is more likely to underestimate the exposure than not
Precision of the judgement as description of remaining uncertainties	<p>The judgement on the interquartile range considers that</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> High uncertainties exist on the factors below and above the median
Experts	Christophe GOLDBECK, José Ángel GÓMEZ RUIZ, Konrad GROB (only 29th Nov 2022), Annette PETERSEN
Observer	EC
Facilitator / Reporter	Olaf MOSBACH-SCHULZ
Date and place of the EKE	The EKE (semi-formal protocol) was done on the 29 th November (Preparation) and 6 th December 2022 (Final EKE) in virtual meetings

178

179

180 **H.2.6. Exposure to MOAH**

181 **H.2.6.1. Evidence**

182 Please refer for the prioritisation of uncertainties to MOSH (section 2.5)

183

184 **H.2.6.2. Evidence review**

185 **Uncertainty: Simplified exposure model for toddlers**

186 **Problem:** The effect of missing or sparse occurrence data, limitation in detection, and processing should
187 be explored

188 **Additional evidence:**

189 To allow the experts to analyse the uncertainties connected to the exposure model a simplified version
190 was constructed, which estimates the exposure through the full diet of an average European toddler.
191 The food categories were limited to the FoodEx level 2. As intake the mean and 95th percentile of the
192 observations in all studies was taken.

193 The simplified model was evaluated with the observations used in the exposure assessment.

194

195 **Mental model:**

196 Furthermore, the experts were asked to review the observed contaminations and map these also on the
197 food categories of the complete diet regarding following uncertainties:

- 198 • Effect of limitations of the analytical methods used for detection, e.g. determination of the LOD
199 for the sum of several MOHs
- 200 • Impute observations below the LOQ/LOD using additional evidence on the presence of
201 contaminations
- 202 • Extrapolate from food categories with observations to categories without observations using
203 additional information on the food categories, e.g. the fat content

204 For each food category a lower and upper limit, and a median estimate was judged. The latter describes
205 an average contamination, which should neither over- nor underestimate the true contamination. The
206 exposure is summed for the complete diet. The results are documented in a separate file.

207 To describe the uncertainties the exposure via the complete diet (mental model) is compared with the
208 result (middle bound) of the simplified model restricted to the observations of the exposure analysis
209 (current analysis). Finally the ratio between the exposure of the complete model and the current analysis
210 is taken as measure of the full uncertainties.

211

212 This exercise indicates that for the mean consumer (average European toddler) the exposure of MOAH
213 via the complete diet is 6% lower (factor 0.94) than calculated in the current exposure analysis with a
214 range from "lower bound" 76% less (factor 0.24) to "upper bound" 130% more (factor 2.30). The
215 exposure to MOAH of the high consumer (P95) toddler is 5% higher (factor 1.05) than calculated in the
216 current exposure analysis with a range from "lower bound" 73% less (factor 0.27) to "upper bound"
217 148% more (factor 2.48).

218

219 **H.2.6.3. Scenario**

220 Please assume the perfect study:

- 221 • Full diet of the age groups is evaluated
- 222 ○ Breastfeeding is excluded from the exposure assessment and will be handled separately

- 223 ○ All non-food pathways are excluded
- 224 • Evaluation is done with the processed food
- 225 • Large, representative European Survey on food consumption and contamination
- 226 • Contaminations are measured with a LOD low enough to captured all contamination / complete
227 data (no observations below LOQ unless no contamination is present)
- 228 • Uncertainties related to the dietary survey methodology are not considered in the uncertainty
229 assessment
- 230 Regarding the existing assessment:
- 231 • In the existing assessment the middle between LB and UB is calculated for each survey. The
232 median of all European survey is used as "Point of departure" for the comparison
- 233 • The exposure estimate in the current assessment is: 0.010 mg/kg MOAH for the mean toddler
234 and 0.016 mg/kg MOSH for the P95 toddler expressed as the middle value between LB and UB
235 and median across all dietary surveys in the comprehensive database.

236

237 **H.2.6.4. EKE questions**

Topic	Description
Parameter	Exposure of toddlers to MOAH
Strata	Age class: Toddlers Substances: MOAH
Question	In comparison to the existing estimated exposure of toddlers to MOAH (expressed as middle value between LB and UB) and the median exposure calculated across all European surveys, what is the relative change of the estimated exposure after assuming no uncertainty in survey methodology (large, representative European Survey on food consumption and contamination) and complete measurements (no data below LOQ, except uncontaminated samples (real zeros))?
Unit	[-], Factor X or 1/X
Operationalisation	The perfect measurements are included in the assessment and the change is observed. The ratio of changed and existing exposure assessment is the answer.

238

239

240

241

H.2.6.5. EKE consensus

242 The following table summarizes the main uncertainties discussed during the EKE session. Additionally
 243 the results of the uncertainty screening and the calculations of the simplified model were used for the
 244 judgement on the EKE questions to cover the overall uncertainties.

245

Uncertainty	Scenario for lower exposure (low factor)	Scenario for higher exposure (high factor)
Low concentration		Detection of concentrations close to LOD/Q show higher uncertainties
Very high number of left-censored data	At the LB, possible underestimation of the true MOAH levels	At the UB, summing LOQs from individual fractions for estimations can result in overestimation of the levels.
Laboratory practise in analysing MOAH		

246

In comparison to the existing estimated exposure of toddlers to MOAH, what is the relative change of the estimated exposure after assuming no uncertainty in survey methodology, and complete measurements?					
	L	Q1	M	Q3	H
Consensus	0.8	1.05	1.3	1.55	1.8

247

248

H.2.6.6. Result report

249 Please see the result table for details. The results used in the final assessment are reported in the
 250 scientific opinion.

251

H.2.6.7. Process documentation

252 The elicitation process on MOSH was also applied for MOAH.

253

H.2.6.8. Discussions

254 The reasoning is documented in the evidence review and summarised in the result table.

255

Overview of the results of the Expert Knowledge Elicitation (Exposure Assessment MOAH)															
Parameter	Exposure of toddlers to MOAH														
Stratification	Age class: Toddlers / Substances: MOAH														
Question	In comparison to the existing estimated exposure of toddlers to MOAH (expressed as middle value between LB and UB) and the median exposure calculated across all European surveys, what is the relative change of the estimated exposure after assuming no uncertainty in survey methodology (large, representative European Survey on food consumption and contamination) and complete measurements (no data below LOQ, except uncontaminated samples (real zeros))?														
Unit	[-]														
Results	P1%	P2.5%	P5%	P10%	P16.7%	P25%	P33.3%	P50%	P66.7%	P75%	P83.3%	P90%	P95%	P97.5%	P99%
EKE consensus	0.800					1.050		1.30		1.55					1.80
EKE results: Risk ratio	0.794	0.813	0.842	0.897	0.967	1.05	1.14	1.30	1.46	1.55	1.63	1.70	1.76	1.79	1.81
Fitted distribution	BetaGeneral(1.0919,1.0919,0.78,1.82)														
<p>Figure (a): Comparison of elicited and fitted values / density function to describe the remaining uncertainties of the parameter</p>								<p>Figure (b): Cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the likelihood of the parameter</p>							

256

257

Summary of the evidence used for the evaluation	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The assessment bases on the European occurrence data^H, and the food consumption of toddlers in the EFSA database A mean and P95 diet of European toddlers was constructed (FoodEx2 level 3) and evaluated using a simplified exposure model The evidence of contamination for each food category in the diet were reviewed. Data gaps were filled by appropriate extrapolation from similar food categories 	
Main uncertainties	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The effect of high levels of left censored data (e.g. excluded from the exposure assessment), few or missing observations is unclear The occurrence data may not be representative for whole European population, e.g. fewer data from Eastern Europe. Some occurrence data are provided from industry, less experienced laboratories, and not following the current measurement standards, and /or analysing food from more recent sampling years Some measurements were done on individual substances and later combined to a value for the group, which increases the possible detection level 	
Reasoning for a scenario which would lead to a reasonable high ratio	<p>The judgement on the upper limit considers that</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Left-censored occurrence data represent contaminations close to the detection level Food categories in the toddlers diet without occurrence data will contribute to the intake Regions (e.g. Eastern Europe) underrepresented in the database of occurrence data show higher concentrations Measurements not following the current standard show lower concentrations Measurements on single compounds (later combined) underestimate the concentration, e.g. in fatty food
Reasoning for a scenario which would lead to a reasonable low ratio	<p>The judgement on the lower limit considers that</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Food categories with high level of left-censored data, with few or none measurements are not contaminated Current exposure may be lower than in the past
Fair estimate as judgement on the weighted evidence	<p>The judgement on the median considers that</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Food categories with few/no measurements show contaminations as similar categories, or “background contaminations” Underestimation of the exposure is more likely than not
Precision of the judgement as description of remaining uncertainties	<p>The judgement on the interquartile range considers that</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> High uncertainties exist on the factors below and above the median
Experts	Christophe GOLDBECK, José Ángel GÓMEZ RUIZ, Konrad GROB (only 29th Nov 2022), Annette PETERSEN
Observer	EC
Facilitator / Reporter	Olaf MOSBACH-SCHULZ
Date and place of the EKE	The EKE (semi-formal protocol) was done on the 29 th November (Preparation) and 6 th December 2022 (Final EKE) in virtual meetings

261 **H.2.7. Third EKE session: Margin of Exposure**

262 **H.2.7.1. Elicitation group**

Role	Name	Contact (e.g. email, phone)
Scientific officer	Marco BINAGLIA	
Elicitor		
Recorder	Marco BINAGLIA	
Expert profile		
	José Ángel GÓMEZ RUIZ	
	Kevin CHIPMAN (Chair)	
	Jan ALEXANDER	
	Christophe GOLDBECK	
	Konrad GROB	
	Annette PETERSEN	
	Heather WALLACE	

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264 **H.2.7.2. Elicitation method**

265 The working group reviewed the combined uncertainty assessment of hazard and exposure and
 266 calculated uncertainty of the MoE. The final statements were agreed in consensus.

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268 **H.2.8. MoE of MOSH**269 **H.2.8.1. Evidence**

270 The uncertainties of the hazard and exposure assessment are passed through the MoE calculation:

271 $MoE = (RefValue * UA_{Hazard}) / (Expo_Mean * UA_{Expo})$

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Overview of the results of the Expert Knowledge Elicitation (Margin of Exposure (MoE) for Toddlers)															
Parameter	MoE of toddlers against MOSH														
Stratification	Age class: Toddlers / Substances: MOSH														
Model	MoE = (RefValue*UA_Hazard) / (Expo_Mean*UA_Expo)														
Unit	[-]														
Results	P1%	P2.5%	P5%	P10%	P16.7%	P25%	P33.3%	P50%	P66.7%	P75%	P83.3%	P90%	P95%	P97.5%	P99%
Hazard assessment (Current assessment 236 mg/kg)															
Uncertainty factor	0.05	0.05	0.06	0.08	0.12	0.17	0.23	0.39	0.60	0.75	0.96	1.19	1.47	1.72	2.00
Distr. Ref. value	11.80	12.74	14.75	19.73	27.88	40.07	54.51	91.11	142.71	178.10	225.70	281.02	347.95	406.23	470.91
Exposure assessment for toddlers (Current assessment: Mean: 0.066 mg/kg / P95: 0.105 mg/kg)															
Uncertainty factor	0.90	0.94	0.96	0.99	1.02	1.05	1.07	1.10	1.13	1.15	1.16	1.18	1.19	1.20	1.21
Distr. Expo Mean	0.060	0.062	0.064	0.066	0.068	0.069	0.071	0.073	0.075	0.076	0.077	0.078	0.079	0.079	0.080
Distr. Expo P95	0.095	0.098	0.101	0.104	0.107	0.110	0.112	0.116	0.119	0.120	0.122	0.124	0.125	0.126	0.127
MoE for toddlers (Current assessment: Mean: 3563 / P95: 2250)															
Distr. MoE Mean	160	176	203	274	385	556	754	1263	1970	2467	3136	3923	4828	5659	6631
Distr. MoE P95	101	111	128	173	243	351	476	798	1244	1558	1980	2477	3048	3573	4186

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H.2.8.2. Evidence review

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Results for different age classes (toddlers, others) and exposure estimates (mean, P95) using the uncertainty factors of toddlers.

	Expo	Certainty of concern	Percentiles of the MoE distribution														
			1.0%	2.5%	5.0%	10.0%	16.7%	25.0%	33.3%	50.0%	66.7%	75.0%	83.3%	90.0%	95.0%	97.5%	99.0%
Toddlers, Mean	0.066	5%	160	176	203	274	385	556	754	1263	1970	2467	3136	3923	4828	5659	6631
Toddlers, P95	0.105	13%	101	111	128	173	243	351	476	798	1244	1558	1980	2477	3048	3573	4186
Infants, Mean	0.069	5%	154	169	195	263	371	535	725	1215	1895	2373	3016	3773	4644	5442	6377
Infants, P95	0.117	15%	91	100	115	155	218	315	427	716	1116	1398	1776	2222	2735	3206	3756
Other children, Mean	0.051	0%	207	228	263	355	500	721	977	1638	2554	3198	4065	5085	6259	7335	8595
Other children, P95	0.086	9%	123	135	156	211	297	428	581	973	1517	1900	2415	3021	3718	4358	5106
Adolescents, Mean	0.026	0%	408	449	518	699	984	1420	1924	3225	5028	6296	8003	10012	12322	14441	16922
Adolescents, P95	0.046	0%	228	251	289	390	549	793	1074	1801	2808	3516	4469	5591	6881	8064	9449
Adults, Mean	0.019	0%	555	610	705	951	1338	1932	2618	4387	6841	8567	10890	13623	16766	19650	23025
Adults, P95	0.035	0%	300	330	381	515	724	1045	1416	2373	3700	4633	5889	7368	9068	10627	12453
Elderly, Mean	0.018	0%	597	657	759	1024	1440	2079	2817	4721	7362	9219	11718	14660	18043	21145	24777
Elderly, P95	0.031	0%	341	375	433	584	821	1186	1607	2693	4199	5258	6684	8362	10291	12061	14133

Very elderly, Mean	0.020	0%	517	569	657	887	1248	1801	2441	4091	6379	7988	10154	12703	15635	18323	21470
Very elderly, P95	0.034	0%	307	338	390	526	740	1068	1448	2427	3784	4738	6023	7534	9273	10867	12734
Pregnant women, Mean	0.017	0%	629	692	800	1079	1518	2191	2969	4977	7760	9717	12352	15452	19018	22288	26116
Pregnant women, P95	0.030	0%	351	386	446	602	847	1222	1656	2775	4328	5419	6888	8617	10606	12430	14565
Lactating women, Mean	0.022	0%	487	535	618	834	1173	1694	2295	3847	5999	7511	9548	11945	14701	17229	20189
Lactating women, P95	0.038	0%	280	308	355	480	675	974	1320	2212	3449	4319	5490	6868	8453	9907	11609
Vegetarians, Mean	0.015	0%	698	767	886	1196	1682	2428	3291	5515	8599	10768	13688	17124	21076	24700	28943
Vegetarians, P95	0.031	0%	338	372	429	579	815	1176	1594	2671	4164	5214	6628	8292	10206	11961	14015

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278 H.2.8.3. Final conclusion

279 The experts agreed on a certainty band for their final conclusions:

- 280 1. Regarding MOSH it is likely to very likely (with 66% to 95% certainty) that neither mean nor high consuming toddlers give reason for concern. The certainty level of
 281 “no concern” was calculated to be 87% for high consuming toddlers, 95% for toddlers with mean intake. Beside high consuming infants (85%) the calculated certainty
 282 level for all other age groups exceeds the values for toddlers

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H.2.9. MoE of MOAH

H.2.9.1. Evidence

The uncertainties of the hazard and exposure assessment are passed through the MoE calculation:

$$\text{MoE} = (\text{RefValue} * \text{UA}_{\text{Hazard}}) / (\text{Expo}_{\text{Mean}} * \text{UA}_{\text{Expo}})$$

Overview of the results of the Expert Knowledge Elicitation (Margin of Exposure (MoE) for Toddlers)															
Parameter	MoE of toddlers against MOAH														
Stratification	Age class: Toddlers / Substances: MOSH														
Model	MoE = (RefValue*UA_Hazard) / (Expo_Mean*UA_Expo)														
Unit	[-]														
Results	P1%	P2.5%	P5%	P10%	P16.7%	P25%	P33.3%	P50%	P66.7%	P75%	P83.3%	P90%	P95%	P97.5%	P99%
Hazard assessment (Current assessment 0.49 mg/kg)															
Uncertainty factor	3.32	3.47	3.91	5.42	8.57	14.20	21.67	42.37	72.40	92.22	116.91	142.29	167.80	185.26	199.87
Distr. Ref. value	1.63	1.70	1.92	2.66	4.20	6.96	10.62	20.76	35.48	45.19	57.29	69.72	82.22	90.78	97.94
Exposure assessment for toddlers (Current assessment: Mean: 0.010 mg/kg / P95: 0.016 mg/kg)															
Uncertainty factor	0.79	0.81	0.84	0.90	0.97	1.05	1.14	1.30	1.46	1.55	1.63	1.70	1.76	1.79	1.81
Distr. Expo Mean	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02
Distr. Expo P95	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03
MoE for toddlers (Current assessment: Mean: 50 / P95:30)															
Distr. MoE Mean	109	128	156	218	341	558	861	1660	2856	3653	4664	5804	7059	8304	9711
Distr. MoE P95	65	77	94	131	204	335	517	997	1715	2194	2801	3485	4239	4987	5831

Figure (a): Distribution functions of MoE for Mean toddlers and P95 toddlers

H.2.9.2. Evidence review

Results for different age classes (toddlers, others) and exposure estimates (mean, P95) using the uncertainty factors of toddlers.

	Expo	Certainty of concern	Percentiles of the MoE distribution														
			1.0%	2.5%	5.0%	10.0%	16.7%	25.0%	33.3%	50.0%	66.7%	75.0%	83.3%	90.0%	95.0%	97.5%	99.0%
Toddlers, Mean	0.009 7	99 %	109	128	156	218	341	558	861	1660	2856	3653	4663	5804	7059	8304	9711
Toddlers, P95	0.016 2	100 %	65	77	94	131	204	335	517	997	1715	2194	2800	3485	4239	4987	5831
Infants, Mean	0.009 8	99 %	108	127	155	217	339	555	856	1651	2841	3633	4637	5772	7020	8258	9657
Infants, P95	0.020 1	100 %	53	62	75	106	165	270	416	803	1382	1768	2256	2808	3415	4018	4698
Other children, Mean	0.007 6	97 %	141	165	201	281	439	719	1109	2140	3682	4709	6011	7482	9099	10705	12518
Other children, P95	0.013 5	100 %	79	93	113	158	247	404	624	1203	2070	2648	3380	4206	5116	6019	7038
Adolescents, Mean	0.004 1	80 %	260	305	371	520	811	1329	2049	3953	6802	8699	11103	13819	16808	19774	23123
Adolescents, P95	0.007 9	97 %	135	158	193	270	421	690	1065	2054	3535	4521	5770	7182	8734	10276	12016
Adults, Mean	0.002 7	66 %	392	459	559	784	1223	2004	3091	5962	10260	13122	16748	20845	25353	29826	34879
Adults, P95	0.005 4	89 %	197	232	282	395	617	1010	1558	3006	5172	6615	8443	10508	12781	15036	17583
Elderly, Mean	0.002 6	64 %	408	479	583	817	1274	2088	3220	6212	10689	13671	17449	21718	26414	31075	36339

Elderly, P95	0.004 8	85 %	222	260	317	444	692	1134	1749	3373	5805	7424	9476	11794	14345	16876	19735
Very elderly, Mean	0.003 1	70 %	346	406	494	693	1081	1771	2732	5269	9067	11596	14801	18422	22405	26359	30824
Very elderly, P95	0.005 3	88 %	199	234	285	399	623	1020	1574	3035	5223	6680	8527	10613	12907	15185	17757
Pregnant women, Mean	0.002 6	64 %	410	481	585	820	1280	2097	3233	6237	10733	13726	17520	21806	26521	31202	36487
Pregnant women, P95	0.005 6	90 %	191	224	273	383	597	978	1509	2910	5007	6404	8174	10174	12374	14558	17024
Lactating women, Mean	0.003 1	70 %	346	406	495	693	1081	1772	2732	5270	9069	11599	14805	18427	22411	26366	30833
Lactating women, P95	0.005 2	87 %	206	242	294	412	643	1053	1625	3134	5393	6897	8803	10957	13326	15677	18333
Vegetarians, Mean	0.002 5	63 %	424	498	606	849	1325	2171	3348	6458	11114	14214	18143	22581	27463	32310	37783
Vegetarians, P95	0.005 3	88 %	200	235	286	401	626	1025	1581	3050	5248	6712	8568	10664	12969	15258	17843

H.2.9.3. Final conclusion

The experts agreed on a certainty band for their final conclusions:

1. Regarding MOAH it is extremely likely (with 99% to 100% certainty) that mean and high consuming toddlers give reason for concern. The certainty level of “concern” was calculated to be 100% for high consuming toddlers, 99% for toddlers with mean intake. For all other age groups it is likely (above 66%) to give reason for concern. The minimal certainty level was calculated for elderly persons with mean intake (64%).